

**PRONE VERSUS SUPINE POSITION FOR LUNG
ULTRASOUND IN THE NEONATES WITH RESPIRATORY
DISTRESS**

By Dr. Y. ROHITH

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IN

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**PRONE VERSUS SUPINE POSITION FOR LUNG ULTRASOUND IN THE
NEONATES WITH RESPIRATORY DISTRESS**

ABBREVIATIONS

ABC - ATP-binding cassette

A-lines - Horizontal artifacts in ultrasound images

ATP - Adenosine triphosphate

B-lines - Vertical artifacts in ultrasound images

CXR - Chest X-ray

ESPNIC - European Society of Paediatric and Neonatal Intensive Care

ENaC - Epithelial sodium channels

LUS - Lung Ultrasound

NICU - Neonatal Intensive Care Unit

NRDS - Neonatal Respiratory Distress Syndrome

PaCO₂ - Partial pressure of carbon dioxide

PCO₂ - Partial pressure of carbon dioxide

PEEP - Positive end-expiratory pressure

POCUS - Point-Of-Care Ultrasound

RDS - Respiratory Distress Syndrome

SP-A - Surfactant Protein A

SP-B - Surfactant Protein B

SP-C - Surfactant Protein C

SP-D - Surfactant Protein D

Spe - Specificity

Sen - Sensitivity

ABSTRACT

Background: Lung Ultrasound (LUS) is a point-of-care, radiation-free diagnostic technique that is easy to use, quick, repeatable, and especially suitable for neonates and critical care settings. It offers significant advantages over conventional chest radiography, including higher sensitivity and specificity for neonatal respiratory disorders without the associated risks of ionizing radiation. Aimed to evaluate and compare LUS scores in prone and supine positions in neonates with respiratory distress and assess the effect of positioning on LUS scores.

Material & Methods: This prospective observational study was conducted over 12 months at the Level IIIA Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU) of BLDE University, Shri B. M. Patil Medical College Hospital, and Research Centre, Vijayapura, Karnataka. Neonates ≥ 29 weeks gestational age with respiratory distress requiring respiratory support within the first 12 hours of life were included. Exclusion criteria were gross congenital anomalies detected antenatally or inability to change position. A total of 103 neonates were enrolled, and LUS was performed in three positions: initial (fLUS), prone or supine (sLUS), and post-change (tLUS). LUS scores were assigned based on a standardized scoring system across six lung zones.

Results: The cohort's mean gestational age was 35.2 weeks, with a gender distribution of 52.4% males and 47.6% females. Delivery modes were primarily LSCS (60.2%) and NVD (34%). Significant correlations were found in blood gas parameters (pH, PaO₂, PaCO₂, bicarbonate, and lactate levels) between prone and supine positions. However, the mean base excess was significantly higher in the supine position. The initial LUS scores were significantly higher than those in the subsequent positions, and significant correlations were observed between clinical, X-ray, and LUS diagnoses, particularly for transient tachypnea of the newborn (TTNB).

Conclusion: LUS in both prone and supine positions offer comparable diagnostic utility for neonates with respiratory distress, with significant correlations in physiological responses and diagnostic imaging findings. While LUS scores and respiratory parameters were largely consistent across positions, the differences in base excess highlight the importance of individualized assessment in positioning for LUS to optimize diagnostic accuracy and clinical outcomes.

Keywords: Lung ultrasound (LUS), Neonatal respiratory distress, Prone position, Supine position, Neonatology, Diagnostic imaging.

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INTRODUCTION

Lung Ultra Sound (LUS) is a point of care, easy to use, radiation free, bedside, quick and repeatable technique. LUS signs vary little by age, which makes it especially suitable for use in neonates and in critical care settings. It is a powerful diagnostic technique and a non-invasive research tool to describe several neonatal respiratory disorders in a qualitative manner.^{1,2}

LUS confers many advantages in neonatology, it allows safe and recurrent assessment of the child's pathology and also the impact of treatment. It also promotes time at the bedside of the critically ill child, which has direct benefits of noting clinical changes promptly and potentially indirect benefits of increasing parental satisfaction.³⁻⁵

Chest radiography is an important imaging modality used for the assessment of neonatal respiratory distress syndrome (NRDS) in newborns, but it causes high exposure to growing neonates to harmful ionizing radiation, which may cause long-term consequences. LUS has the advantage of the absence of harmful ionizing radiation exposure. It has higher sensitivity (Sen) and specificity (Spe). It is a cost effective, radiation-free, and easy-to-operate tool that can be repeatedly performed at the bedside.

It has many such advantages over conventional chest radiography for which this study is being conducted to emphasize the importance and role of LUS in regular practice of neonatology. Hence this study aimed to assess lung ultrasound (LUS) in the prone position and to compare it with the supine position in neonates with respiratory distress. Although LUS is well-documented for its efficacy in various neonatal respiratory disorders, its utility across different body positions remains underexplored. Traditional imaging, such as

chest radiography, requires specific positioning which may not always be feasible or ideal for neonates with severe respiratory distress. LUS, however, can be performed in various positions (supine, prone, lateral) and has the potential to offer distinct diagnostic advantages depending on the neonate's position. Understanding the impact of positioning on LUS scores and the resultant diagnostic accuracy is essential for optimizing its use in clinical practice.

Hence, present study aimed to comparison of scores of the lung ultrasound (LUS) in the prone position and to compare it with the supine position in neonates with respiratory distress.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Neonatal respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) is a prevalent cause of respiratory difficulties in newborns, typically emerging within hours of birth and most often right after delivery. This condition primarily impacts preterm infants but can occasionally affect those born at full term. The likelihood of RDS decreases as the gestational age increases, with more severe forms occurring in smaller and more premature infants. Despite advancements in treatment options—such as antenatal corticosteroids, surfactants, and sophisticated neonatal respiratory care—RDS remains a significant contributor to morbidity and mortality among preterm infants.

Lung development

Normal fetal alveolar development progresses through several distinct stages:

Embryonic Period: Around 26 days of gestation, the foetal lung first appears as a protrusion from the foregut, marking the beginning of the embryonic stage. By 33 days, initial lung branching occurs, forming the future main bronchi, which start to extend into the surrounding mesenchyme. This early branching paves the way for the formation of segmental bronchi as the lung advances to the next developmental stage.

Pseudoglandular Stage: Spanning from the 5th to the 16th weeks of gestation, the pseudoglandular stage involves 15 to 20 generations of airway branching, extending from the main segmental bronchi to the terminal bronchioles. By the end of this stage, the airways are encircled by loosely arranged mesenchyme containing a few blood vessels. The airway lining consists of glycogen-rich, morphologically undifferentiated epithelial

cells that vary from columnar to cuboidal shapes. Epithelial differentiation progresses from the centre outward, with the proximal airways exhibiting the most differentiation.

Canalicular Stage: Between the 16th and 25th weeks of gestation, the canalicular stage marks the transition from a non-viable to a potentially viable lung. This stage is characterized by the development of respiratory bronchioles and alveolar ducts in the gas exchange region. The mesenchyme surrounding the airways becomes more vascular and condenses, leading to the fusion of the capillary and epithelial basement membranes. After 20 weeks, cuboidal epithelial cells begin differentiating into alveolar type II cells, forming cytoplasmic lamellar bodies, which indicate surfactant production from glycogen and storage within these bodies.⁶

Saccular Stage: Beginning around 24 weeks of gestation, the saccular stage introduces the potential for viability as large, primitive alveoli capable of gas exchange form. This stage involves the outgrowth of septae, which subdivides terminal saccules into anatomic alveoli where air exchange occurs. The number of alveoli increases from none at 32 weeks to between 50 and 150 million in full-term infants and reaches approximately 300 million in adults. Alveolar development continues for at least two years post-birth.

Pulmonary Surfactant: Respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) primarily stems from a lack of pulmonary surfactant, a substance whose production is developmentally regulated. In the fetal stage, the lungs are filled with fluid and do not function in respiration until birth. As the fetus prepares for breathing air, surfactant production begins around the 20th week of gestation. This surfactant decreases alveolar surface tension, which aids in alveolar expansion and minimizes the risk of alveolar collapse (atelectasis).⁷

The leading cause of surfactant deficiency is preterm birth due to the developmental timing of surfactant production. Additionally, genetic mutations affecting surfactant proteins SP-B and SP-C , as well as the ATP-binding cassette (ABC) transporter A3 (ABCA3) , can result in surfactant deficiencies or dysfunction, potentially causing hereditary respiratory failure in full-term infants.^{8,9}

Pulmonary surfactant is primarily a complex lipid mixture (90%), mainly phospholipids, with about 10% protein content.

- **Lipid:** Approximately 70% of the surfactant's lipid content is phosphatidylcholine, with around 60% of this being disaturated palmitoyl phosphatidylcholine, the key component in reducing alveolar surface tension.¹⁰
- **Protein:** There are four identified surfactant-specific proteins with partially understood functions. These include the hydrophobic proteins SP-B and SP-C, and the hydrophilic proteins SP-A and SP-D.¹¹⁻¹³
 - **SP-A:** A collectin family protein, SP-A plays a role in innate immunity and inflammation regulation in the lung, aiding in the phagocytosis of pathogens and their clearance by macrophages. No known cases of SP-A deficiency have been identified. In preterm lungs SP-A levels are low nevertheless, they rise in response to corticosteroid therapy. SP-A knockout mice have normal lung function and surfactant metabolism, indicating its non-critical role in surfactant metabolism regulation. SP-A is absent in current RDS treatment surfactants.

- **SP-B:** This protein aids lipid absorption at the surface and enhances surfactant's ability to lower surface tension. Animals with SP-B antibodies develop respiratory failure. Homozygous SP-B deficiency is rare and usually lethal in full-term infants. SP-B and SP-C are included in commercial surfactant formulations.⁸
- **SP-C:** Humans lacking SP-C do not show respiratory distress at birth but develop progressive interstitial pulmonary fibrosis from infancy to early childhood. SP-C deficient mice display normal lung functioning at birth but develops progressive lung disease and emphysema as they age. SP-C deficiency in these mice leads to injuries in type II cells due to misprocessed SP-C. SP-B and SP-C likely work together to enhance the rapid adsorption and distribution of phospholipids, aiding in surface tension reduction and alveolar stability at low lung volumes.
- **SP-D:** Similar to SP-A, SP-D is a hydrophilic protein and part of the collectin family, contributing to innate host defense by binding to pathogens and facilitating their removal. SP-D absence leads to increased surfactant lipid pools and emphysema, but does not majorly impact surfactant function in mice. Experiments on preterm lambs treated with recombinant SP-D have shown reduced lung inflammation and improved surfactant function, indicating potential for human treatment.^{14,15}
- **Synthesis, Secretion, and Absorption:** Surfactant is synthesized in the alveolar type II cells, beginning with phospholipid production in the endoplasmic reticulum. This is followed by processing through the Golgi apparatus, culminating

in the formation of lamellar bodies. Within these lamellar bodies, phospholipids combine with surfactant proteins SP-B and SP-C to create the surfactant lipoprotein complex. The lamellar bodies then migrate to the apical surface of the type II cell and are secreted into the alveoli via exocytosis.

- Upon entering the alveoli, the lamellar bodies unfold, allowing the surfactant complex to form a lipoprotein structure called tubular myelin, which includes SP-A, SP-B, SP-C, and phospholipids. This structure is crucial for forming the surface film that reduces alveolar surface tension within the alveoli and airways. The secreted surfactant is then taken back into the type II cells from the airspaces through an endocytic process, where it is incorporated into multivesicular bodies and then reprocessed into lamellar bodies. The recycling of both endogenous and exogenous surfactant is vital for maintaining the surfactant pool.

Prematurity: In preterm infants, reduced quantity and quality of surfactant lead to diminished surfactant activity, resulting in respiratory distress syndrome (RDS).^{16,17}

The surfactant produced by preterm infants not only diminishes in quantity with lower gestational age but also shows reduced effectiveness compared to that from term infants due to differences in lipid and protein composition:

- **Lipid Composition:** Surfactant from immature lungs has higher levels of phosphatidylinositol (10% compared to 2% in mature lungs) and lower levels of phosphatidylglycerol (less than 1% compared to 10%). The surfactant from mature lungs, with its higher phosphatidylglycerol content, exhibits better surface activity.

Phosphatidylglycerol levels rise in amniotic fluid after 35 weeks of gestation and serve as a marker for fetal lung maturity.

Various methods are available to evaluate fetal lung maturity, such as the lecithin/sphingomyelin (L/S) ratio and lamellar body counts. Surfactant production begins around the 20th week of gestation, marked by the appearance of lamellar bodies in the epithelial cells of the airways. Clinically, lamellar body counts in amniotic fluid can also be used to assess fetal lung maturity and surfactant production.

Protein Content: Surfactant in preterm lungs has a lower protein content relative to surfactant lipids. Typically, type II cells with lamellar bodies appear in the human lung after 20 weeks of gestation, but significant surfactant protein mRNA expression only occurs later. The expression of the four surfactant proteins varies with gestational age: SP-A increases after 32 weeks, SP-B after 34 weeks, SP-C mRNA is highly expressed at the tips of branching airways early in lung development, and SP-D mRNA expression remains low until late gestation.

Administering antenatal glucocorticoids can lower the risk of RDS in preterm infants by promoting lung maturation. This is achieved by enhancing the development of lung architecture and inducing enzymes that stimulate phospholipid synthesis and surfactant release.

Pathophysiology

The primary abnormality in RDS is surfactant deficiency. In premature lungs, inadequate surfactant leads to high surface tension, causing lung instability at end-expiration, low

lung volume, and reduced compliance. These changes impair lung function, resulting in hypoxemia due to mismatched ventilation and perfusion, primarily from widespread lung collapse (atelectasis) and additional ventilation/perfusion mismatches from intrapulmonary and extrapulmonary right-to-left shunts.

Surfactant deficiency also triggers lung inflammation and injury to the respiratory epithelium, potentially leading to pulmonary edema and increased airway resistance. These issues exacerbate lung injury and impair function further. Moreover, abnormal fluid absorption hampers the clearance of liquid in the injured lung, contributing to edema that impairs gas exchange.

Surfactant deficiency—In preterm infants, the lack of surfactant is the main cause of RDS, as the absence of surfactant increases the pressure needed to open alveoli and causes alveolar instability at low volumes, leading to alveolar collapse and widespread atelectasis. (Refer to the 'Prematurity' section above.)

The relationship between inflating pressure, surface tension, and the radius of curvature is described by modeling a distal alveolus as a sphere connected to a distal airway, as explained by LaPlace's law. According to LaPlace's law, the pressure (P) required to keep the sphere open is proportional to the surface tension (T) and inversely proportional to the radius (R) of the sphere:

$$P = 2T/R$$

When surface tension is high and alveolar volume is low (i.e., the radius is small), such as at end-expiration, the pressure needed to keep the alveolus open is high. If this increased

pressure cannot be generated, the alveolus collapses. When alveolar collapse occurs throughout the lung, diffuse atelectasis ensues, leading to hypoxemia. Pulmonary surfactant reduces surface tension, even at low volumes, decreasing the pressure required and thus maintaining alveolar volume and stability.

Inflammation and lung injury—Animal studies suggest that inflammation plays a role in RDS pathogenesis, showing that surfactant deficiency leads to rapid neutrophil accumulation and pulmonary edema. Neutrophil depletion in these models prevented edema. Surfactant deficiency also causes atelectasis, which may damage the respiratory epithelium and alveolar capillary endothelium, triggering a cytokine-mediated inflammatory response. Additional injury may occur due to positive pressure ventilation or excessive oxidant exposure. Inflammation and lung injury can lead to protein-rich pulmonary fluid accumulation that deactivates any present surfactant, worsening the surfactant deficiency.

Pulmonary edema—In RDS infants, pulmonary edema can result from several factors:

- Inflammation and lung injury (refer to the above section on 'Inflammation and lung injury').

- Reduced pulmonary fluid absorption—In fetuses, lung fluid is actively transported into potential airspaces via chloride channels. In preparation for birth and breathing air, the lung transitions from secretion to absorption. Fluid absorption is mediated by epithelial sodium channels (ENaC), whose expression increases with gestational age and the rise in surfactant production. In preterm infants, insufficient ENaC may lead to fluid retention, similar to the transient tachypnea of the newborn.

-Low urine output—Infants with RDS typically have low urine output, contributing to fluid retention in the initial days, which can worsen pulmonary edema. Some may experience hyponatremia due to increased free water. Infants recovering from RDS often undergo spontaneous diuresis between the second and fourth day, followed by improved lung function.

Surfactant Inactivation and Pulmonary Effects in RDS

Surfactant inactivation compounds the challenges of reduced surfactant production and the synthesis of a less effective surfactant, further diminishing the functional surfactant pool.

Key contributors to surfactant inactivation include:

Presence of Meconium and Blood: Surfactant activity can be impaired by meconium and blood within the alveoli. This is a more common problem in term infants with meconium aspiration syndrome than in preterm infants suffering from surfactant deficiency.

Proteinaceous Oedema and Inflammatory Products: These factors can expedite the transformation of surfactant into its inactive vesicular form. This conversion process is further accelerated by oxidative stress and mechanical ventilation, particularly when high tidal volumes are used without adequate positive end-expiratory pressure (PEEP) .

Pulmonary Function and Gas Exchange Impairments

The primary adverse effects of surfactant deficiency on pulmonary function include reduced compliance and decreased lung volume (functional residual capacity), largely due to atelectasis. Additionally, pulmonary edema and inflammation may also contribute. Increased lung resistance likely arises from airway compression by interstitial edema and

damage to airways caused by the elevated pressures required to expand the noncompliant alveoli.

Exogenous surfactant therapy can mitigate these issues by improving lung compliance and volume, and by reducing lung resistance (refer to the section on surfactant therapy in "Respiratory Distress Syndrome (RDS) in Preterm Infants: Management").

Hypoxemia and Ventilation-Perfusion Mismatch

In RDS, hypoxemia predominantly results from ventilation-perfusion mismatch and intrapulmonary right-to-left shunting of blood through poorly ventilated lung areas. Extrapulmonary shunting is also common, typically occurring across the foramen ovale and patent ductus arteriosus. The degree of hypoxemia from shunting versus inadequate alveolar ventilation depends on the extent of hypoxic pulmonary vasoconstriction and the size of the under ventilated lung regions. Even though minute ventilation may increase, alveolar ventilation is reduced because much of the lung remains collapsed and inadequately ventilated, leading to elevated arterial partial pressure of carbon dioxide (PaCO_2) and respiratory acidosis. Metabolic acidosis may also develop due to lactic acid production from anaerobic metabolism in response to hypoxemia and impaired tissue perfusion.

Clinical presentation of patients

The clinical manifestations of respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) primarily stem from abnormal pulmonary function and hypoxemia, which arise due to deficient surfactant production, a developmental disorder evident within minutes to hours after birth. Without treatment, RDS typically worsens over the initial 48 hours of life. Some infants initially

appear well at birth but develop respiratory distress and cyanosis shortly thereafter, likely due to inadequate or inactivated surfactant.

Infants affected by RDS, usually premature, present with signs of respiratory distress including:

- **Tachypnea:** Rapid breathing.
- **Nasal Flaring:** Indicative of increased use of accessory respiratory muscles and reduced respiratory system resistance.
- **Expiratory Grunting:** Occurs as a result of exhaling against a partially closed glottis, which helps maintain end-expiratory lung volume.
- **Retractions:** 'Intercostal, subxiphoid, and subcostal retractions' due to the compliant rib cage being drawn inward during inspiration to counteract the high intrathoracic pressures required for expanding the non-compliant lungs.
- **Cyanosis:** Resulting from intra- and extra-pulmonary right-to-left shunting of blood (refer to 'Pulmonary function and gas exchange' above).

During physical examination, breath sounds are typically diminished upon auscultation, and infants may appear pale with reduced peripheral pulses. In the first 24 to 48 hours, urine output is often low, and peripheral edema may be present.

Laboratory findings

Laboratory findings associated with neonatal Respiratory Distress Syndrome (RDS) include several key aspects beyond radiographic evidence:

- **Chest Radiography:** Standard for diagnosing RDS, reveals low lung volume and a characteristic diffuse reticulogranular ground glass appearance with air bronchograms in preterm infants presenting with respiratory distress

Figure 1: Chest radiograph of neonatal respiratory distress syndrome

- **Arterial Blood Gas Measurements:** Typically show hypoxemia, which responds to supplemental oxygen. Initially, the ‘partial pressure of carbon dioxide (PCO₂)’ may be normal or slightly elevated but tends to increase as the disease progresses.
- **Hyponatremia:** Can develop as RDS worsens due to water retention, though careful fluid management can mitigate this. This electrolyte imbalance tends to improve with fluid restriction.

These laboratory findings support the clinical diagnosis of RDS and guide management strategies aimed at improving oxygenation and fluid balance in affected neonates.

Chest imaging

Chest imaging modalities play crucial roles in diagnosing and assessing the severity of Respiratory Distress Syndrome (RDS) in neonates:

Chest Radiography:

- **Low lung volumes:** Typically observed due to alveolar collapse.
- **Diffuse reticulogranular ground glass appearance with air bronchograms:** Characteristic findings indicating widespread atelectasis and aerated airways, contributing to a hazy lung appearance.
- **Pulmonary edema:** Contributes to the diffuse appearance seen on radiographs.
- **Pneumothorax and air leaks:** Uncommon initially, more likely observed with improving lung compliance.

Chest Ultrasound:

- **Lung consolidation with air bronchograms:** Key ultrasound feature characterized by uneven hypoechoic areas with visible air-filled bronchi. Bilateral involvement is common, with posterior lung regions often affected.¹⁸⁻²¹ Severity correlates with the extent of consolidation, ranging from focal subpleural involvement to diffuse patterns resembling "white lung."²¹⁻²³
- **Pleural line abnormalities:** Abnormal appearance with disappearance of A-lines.

- **Interstitial involvement:** Nonconsolidated lung areas may show comet tail B-lines and signs of alveolar interstitial syndrome.
- **Pleural effusions:** Seen in a minority of cases, either unilateral or bilateral.²⁴

Diagnostic and Clinical Utility: These imaging findings aid in confirming the diagnosis of RDS and assessing its severity. Chest ultrasound is particularly valuable for its ability to detect subtle lung changes and monitor disease progression, offering a complementary approach to chest radiography in neonatal care settings.^{23,25}

Lung ultrasonography (LUS) has revolutionized clinical practice in neonatology by overcoming historical limitations associated with imaging lung air spaces. Traditionally, ultrasonography was deemed ineffective for lung examination due to air's ability to scatter ultrasound waves. However, since its introduction into adult medicine in 1995, LUS has gained significant traction for its accuracy, reliability, real-time capability, and cost-effectiveness, all without ionizing radiation. Over the past decade, there has been a notable surge in reports highlighting LUS's application in neonatology.²⁶

Recent studies have underscored LUS's potential to entirely replace conventional chest X-rays (CXR) in Neonatal Intensive Care Units (NICUs). A clinical practice report spanning three years, published in 2020, advocated for LUS as a comprehensive alternative to CXR within NICU settings. This shift reflects LUS's ability to provide detailed, radiation-free imaging of lung conditions in neonates, facilitating timely diagnosis and monitoring.^{1,2,27,28}

Figure 2: Division of lung fields

To enhance visualization of the neonatal lung, particularly in infants with low gestational age or small birth weight, the use of a high-frequency (≥ 10 MHz) linear array transducer is recommended for lung ultrasonography (LUS). This approach allows for detailed imaging due to the higher resolution capabilities of the probe.

During LUS examinations, neonates are typically placed in supine, prone, or lateral positions depending on their state of rest. Each hemithorax is divided into three distinct regions—anterior (A), lateral (L), and posterior (P)—by reference to the anterior and posterior axillary lines. Within each region, further subdivision into upper and lower sections aids in systematic scanning.^{29,30}

For optimal imaging, both longitudinal and transverse scans are performed with the probe oriented perpendicular to the ribs across all regions. This comprehensive approach enables thorough assessment of lung conditions and facilitates differential diagnoses in neonatal respiratory distress within the first 24 hours of life.

Comparative studies have demonstrated a high level of agreement between LUS and chest X-ray (CXR) findings in these cases, underscoring the utility of LUS as a reliable diagnostic tool. Guidelines from 'the European Society of Paediatric and Neonatal Intensive Care (ESPNIC)' advocate for the standardized use of point-of-care ultrasound (POCUS), including LUS, in newborns and children. Updated specifications and guidelines for neonatal LUS, recently published, aim to improve consistency among healthcare providers in diagnostic accuracy and enhance overall patient outcomes.^{31,32}

By facilitating standardized protocols and promoting interobserver agreement, these advancements in neonatal LUS contribute significantly to clinical practice, ensuring effective management and care for neonatal respiratory conditions.

Normal lung view

In conventional ultrasound practice, the air-filled lung tissue presents a high acoustic impedance, causing most ultrasound waves to be absorbed rather than reflected.³³ However, ultrasound waves that do reflect at the pleural-lung interface allow visualization of the pleura as a smooth, regular echogenic line known as the "pleural line." Normally, in healthy preterm and term newborns, this pleural line should be less than 1 mm thick.³⁴ During breathing, the pleural line moves synchronously, a phenomenon referred to as

"lung sliding", which indicates normal lung function and is easily observed in real-time ultrasound imaging.

The repetitive reflection of ultrasound waves between the pleura and the probe generates horizontal artifacts known as "A-lines". These artifacts appear parallel to the pleural line, spaced evenly apart, and are characteristic of normal lung tissue. Additionally, in the lungs of neonates, particularly within 48 hours after birth or longer in premature infants, vertical reverberation artifacts known as "B-lines" may be present. These B-lines originate from ultrasound waves reflected at the alveolar air-liquid interface and extend vertically from the pleural line to the edge of the ultrasound screen. They typically disappear once lung fluid is absorbed and are not found in normal lungs of older children or adults.^{35,36}

The presence of A-lines and lung sliding in ultrasound images indicates the absence of significant lung pathology in the scanned area. This ability to detect normal lung characteristics using ultrasound, including the absence of A-lines and lung sliding, is crucial for evaluating neonatal respiratory health non-invasively and in real-time.

(A) Pleural line: the pleura is visualized as a smooth, regular echogenic line; A-lines: equidistant, horizontal, and echogenic lines distal to the pleural line. (B) B-line: vertical hyperechoic artifacts arising from the pleural line.

Figure 3: Normal lung pattern on lung ultrasonography.

Respiratory distress syndrome

Neonatal respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) is a frequent cause of respiratory failure and early mortality in newborns, primarily affecting those born prematurely. It arises due to physiological and structural immaturity of the lungs. The primary etiology of neonatal RDS is recognized as a deficiency in pulmonary surfactant in premature infants. Management typically involves the administration of pulmonary surfactant and mechanical ventilation for severe cases of neonatal RDS.³⁷⁻³⁹

Figure 4 illustrates that lung consolidation with air bronchograms is the characteristic appearance of neonatal RDS in lung ultrasound (LUS). The extent of lung consolidation correlates with the severity of the condition. Longitudinal scans often reveal bilateral "white lung," also known as alveolar-interstitial syndrome (AIS), characterized by prominent B-lines across all examined regions. The pleural line appears thick, irregular, or indistinct. Additionally, severe cases may exhibit pleural effusion and lung pulse, where lung sliding ceases and pulmonary tissues move synchronously with heart pulsations.⁴⁰⁻⁴³ Lung pulse serves as a significant ultrasound marker indicating severe lung consolidation, such as atelectasis. It's important to note that the LUS findings of neonatal RDS can vary between the lungs bilaterally and even within different regions of the same lung.

(A) Pleural line is thick, irregular, or blurred. Lung consolidation with the air bronchogram is the most typical appearance of neonatal RDS. (B) white lung is derived from the emerged compact B-lines.

Figure 4: Respiratory distress syndrome on lung ultrasonography

Lung ultrasound (LUS) has demonstrated remarkable diagnostic utility in neonatal respiratory distress syndrome (RDS), as indicated by a comprehensive review of multiple studies. It consistently exhibits high sensitivity, specificity, and positive and negative predictive values well exceeding 90% for diagnosing RDS in neonates.^{40,44} Moreover, LUS has proven reliable in assessing the severity of RDS and predicting the need for admission to the Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU). By facilitating ongoing monitoring of RDS progression, LUS also contributes to minimizing the use of ionizing radiation.⁴⁵⁻⁴⁷

Despite the established benefits of surfactant therapy for preterm infants with RDS, accurately identifying neonates who would benefit from surfactant remains a clinical challenge. Recently developed LUS scoring systems have emerged as effective tools for predicting the requirement for surfactant treatment in neonatal RDS cases.⁴⁸⁻⁵¹ Evaluations based on these scores have shown that poractant alfa yields more favorable outcomes compared to beractant, and both are superior to calfactant in terms of treatment efficacy. These findings underscore LUS's potential to inform treatment decisions in neonatal RDS management.⁴⁸

Nevertheless, the applicability of LUS scoring systems in routine clinical practice is constrained by existing study limitations. To establish LUS scores as standard tools for predicting surfactant therapy in newborns with RDS, further large-scale, multicenter studies with robust designs are warranted (46, 47). These efforts are essential for confirming the reliability and generalizability of LUS scores across diverse neonatal populations.

Transient tachypnea of newborn

Transient tachypnea of the newborn (TTN), often referred to as "wet lung," arises from delayed clearance of lung fluid post-birth. This condition is particularly associated with elective cesarean sections and premature birth, affecting the ENac function and causing respiratory distress that typically resolves within 24-48 hours. Pulmonary edema, a hallmark of TTN, is identified by LUS through characteristic findings such as double lung point (DLP), alveolar-interstitial syndrome (AIS), or white lung patterns bilaterally.⁵²⁻⁵⁵ The presence of a regular pleural line and absence of significant subpleural consolidation help distinguish TTN from other conditions like RDS and pneumonia. LUS demonstrates

superior diagnostic accuracy compared to traditional chest X-rays, especially in detecting pulmonary edema and differentiating between TTN and RDS, thus ensuring appropriate treatment for neonates with respiratory distress.⁵⁶⁻⁵⁹

Double lung point: there is a sharp change in echogenicity as a result of the abundance of B-lines between the upper and the lower lung fields.

'Figure 5': Transient tachypnea of the newborn on lung ultrasonography

Pneumonia

Neonatal pneumonia poses a significant health risk in developing countries, with respiratory distress as a common symptom. Its diagnosis is often challenging due to nonspecific radiographic findings that overlap with conditions like RDS and TTN. Clinical laboratory tests are essential for accurate differentiation. Although less explored in neonates compared to adults and children, lung ultrasound (LUS) has shown promise in diagnosing pneumonia. Key LUS features include “subpleural consolidations with irregular margins, air bronchograms, abnormal pleural lines, absence of lung sliding, and pleural effusion”. Studies have demonstrated LUS's high sensitivity and specificity in diagnosing neonatal pneumonia, with findings of large consolidated areas and air bronchograms achieving perfect diagnostic accuracy. LUS also aids in monitoring disease progression and severity, making it a valuable tool in neonatal intensive care settings for diagnosing infectious pneumonia and ventilator-associated pneumonia (VAP).⁶⁰⁻⁶²

Ultrasound shows irregular areas of lung consolidation with air bronchograms, disappearance of the pleural line, and A-lines.

'Figure 6': Pneumonia on lung ultrasonography.

Meconium Aspiration Syndrome (MAS):

Meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS) occurs in term/post-term neonates when they inhale meconium-stained amniotic fluid, causing varying degrees of respiratory distress. It is associated with risk factors like birth asphyxia and cesarean delivery. Diagnosis involves clinical manifestations, laboratory tests, and radiographic findings, often requiring supportive treatments like mechanical ventilation and surfactant administration.

Lung ultrasound (LUS) features of MAS, such as irregular subpleural consolidations with air bronchograms, coalescent B-lines, and abnormal pleural lines, show similarities to pneumonia but can be differentiated by the bilateral nature of consolidations in MAS. LUS has demonstrated high sensitivity and specificity in diagnosing MAS, aiding prompt treatment decisions in neonatal intensive care.⁶³⁻⁶⁵

Air Leak Syndromes:

Air leak syndromes, including pneumothorax, pneumomediastinum, and pulmonary interstitial emphysema, are common in neonates due to fragile lungs and mechanical ventilation. Pneumothorax, the most frequent type, can occur in up to 30% of neonates with lung pathologies or on ventilation. Traditional imaging methods like chest X-ray (CXR) have been pivotal in diagnosis, but LUS is increasingly recognized for its diagnostic accuracy in pneumothorax. LUS characteristics of pneumothorax include absence of lung sliding, B-lines, and presence of A-lines, with the lung point marking the boundary between normal and abnormal lung patterns. LUS has shown sensitivity and specificity comparable to CXR in diagnosing neonatal pneumothorax, making it a valuable tool for early detection and management in clinical settings. Further prospective studies are necessary to validate its widespread clinical application.^{66,67}

Figure 7: Pneumothorax on lung ultrasonography.

Bronchopulmonary Dysplasia (BPD):

Bronchopulmonary dysplasia (BPD) is a significant chronic respiratory complication primarily affecting extremely low-birth-weight infants, with an incidence ranging from 48% to 68% among those born before 28 weeks of gestation. This condition arises due to an imbalance between lung injury and repair processes in the developing immature lung, exacerbated by various prenatal, perinatal, and postnatal factors. Despite ongoing research, there is currently no cure for BPD, and affected infants often require long-term oxygen therapy, which can impact their cardiopulmonary function throughout life. While several

potential biomarkers and imaging modalities, including chest radiographs, have been explored for predicting BPD, none have been widely adopted in clinical practice. Lung ultrasound (LUS) shows promise as a tool for early prediction of BPD, potentially offering valuable insights into disease progression and management strategies. Further studies are needed to validate its efficacy and establish standardized protocols for its use in clinical settings.⁶⁸⁻⁷¹

Figure 8: Bronchopulmonary dysplasia on lung ultrasonography.

Atelectasis:

Atelectasis, a condition marked by the collapse and insufficient aeration of lung tissue, is commonly observed in neonates and often complicates respiratory conditions like RDS, MAS, and pneumonia. Rather than being an isolated disease, it typically arises due to underlying pulmonary or thoracic issues, leading to neonatal dyspnea and prolonged illness. The main mechanism causing atelectasis in infants is airway obstruction. Prolonged atelectasis can result in secondary complications, such as infections and bronchial damage, necessitating treatment strategies tailored to its cause and severity. Traditional diagnostic tools include chest X-ray (CXR), CT scans, and bronchoscopy. However, lung ultrasound (LUS) is increasingly used for diagnosing neonatal atelectasis, offering a radiation-free alternative. LUS reveals characteristic features like extensive lung consolidation with bronchograms, abnormal pleural lines, absence of A-lines and lung sliding, and the presence of a lung pulse. These ultrasound findings help distinguish atelectasis from other conditions and aid in monitoring the disease's progression while minimizing exposure to ionizing radiation.⁷²⁻⁷⁴

Figure 9: Atelectasis on lung ultrasonography.

1. Effects on Gas Exchange and Lung Aeration:⁷³

- **Prone Position:**

- **Improvement in Gas Exchange:** Pronation enhances the distribution of pulmonary blood flow and optimizes ventilation-perfusion matching. This

results in improved oxygenation and lung aeration, particularly beneficial in conditions like respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) and bronchopulmonary dysplasia (BPD).

- **Lung Recruitment:** Pronation facilitates the re-expansion of collapsed alveoli by promoting more uniform lung expansion. This is evidenced by a reduction in LUS scores, which correlates with improved oxygenation and reduced need for respiratory support.

- **Supine Position:**

- **Baseline State:** In the supine position, gravitational forces can lead to compression of the dorsal lung regions, potentially worsening atelectasis and hypoxemia, especially in compromised neonates.
- **Effect on LUS Scores:** LUS scores are generally higher in the supine position compared to the prone position immediately after repositioning, indicating less effective lung aeration.⁷³

2. LUS Findings in Different Positions:

- **Prone Position:**

- **Reduced Consolidation:** Prone positioning often shows less consolidation and more uniform lung aeration on LUS.

- **Changes in Pleural Line:** There may be less distortion and more consistent pleural sliding, indicating better lung expansion and less alveolar collapse.
- **Supine Position:**
 - **Increased Consolidation:** LUS in the supine position frequently reveals increased consolidation and atelectasis, particularly in dependent lung regions.
 - **Pleural Line Abnormalities:** Greater irregularity in pleural lines and reduced lung sliding, reflecting poorer lung expansion and greater alveolar collapse.⁷³

Utility, Advantages, and Disadvantages:

Utility:

- **Diagnostic Accuracy:** Both prone and supine positions provide complementary views in LUS. Prone LUS can be especially useful for assessing posterior lung fields and for conditions like BPD where dorsal lung regions may be more affected.
- **Monitoring and Management:** LUS in different positions helps monitor changes in lung aeration and the effectiveness of therapeutic interventions such as mechanical ventilation and prone positioning itself.⁷³

Advantages:

- **Prone Position:**

- **Improved Oxygenation:** Pronation enhances oxygenation and lung aeration, leading to better clinical outcomes in neonates with respiratory distress.
- **Lung Recruitment:** Encourages re-expansion of atelectatic areas, which is crucial in the management of RDS and other forms of neonatal respiratory distress.
- **Reduced Ventilator Dependence:** Can decrease the need for high ventilatory pressures, reducing the risk of ventilator-induced lung injury.

- **Supine Position:**

- **Ease of Access:** Facilitates easier access for other medical procedures and assessments, such as central line placement or abdominal surgery.
- **Standardization:** Offers a consistent position for routine assessments and interventions in many clinical protocols.

Disadvantages:

- **Prone Position:**

- **Practical Challenges:** Repositioning neonates can be logistically challenging and requires careful monitoring to avoid complications such as accidental extubation or dislodgement of lines.

- **Limited Access:** Prone positioning may limit access to the chest and abdomen, complicating other medical procedures and monitoring.
- **Supine Position:**
 - **Potential for Deterioration:** May exacerbate atelectasis and worsen ventilation-perfusion mismatch, particularly in neonates with severe respiratory distress.
 - **Inferior Lung Aeration:** Generally less effective in promoting uniform lung aeration compared to the prone position, which may impact the clinical management of lung diseases.⁷³

Various articles discussing role of Lung Ultrasound;

Copetti et al. diagnosed respiratory distress syndrome accompanied by three ultrasonography findings that are present simultaneously: “abnormalities of the pleural line, white lung image, and absence of spared areas in all lung fields”. This profile had a sensitivity and specificity of 100% in their series of 55 premature infants. The high diagnostic accuracy may allow a better individualized surfactant administration, saving costs and minimizing the duration of ineffective breathing.⁷⁵

Howard et al., (2007) demonstrated a statistically significantly higher overall patient satisfaction in the group who received bedside ultrasound (mean difference 0.46 with a confidence interval of 95% CI, 0.17–0.75). Given that POCUS promotes time at the bedside with the child and family and offers immediate feedback, it is highly likely to stimulate communication and thus foster improved relationships between the clinical team and family.⁷⁶

Oktem et al. (2022) emphasized the importance of LUS in monitoring NRDS treatment. Repeated CXR for infants in a short time is unethical and harmful due to the increased exposure to ionizing radiation. Gargani et al. showed that sonographic abnormalities in the lung precede PaO₂/FiO₂ changes in an animal model. Therefore, LUS can be easily used for the early detection of patients with NRDS before clinical deterioration and improve the clinical progression and prognosis.²⁴

In a study conducted by Ibrahim M et al., (2016) to assess the diagnosis of neonatal transient tachypnea and its differentiation from other cause of respiratory disorders. In a study of 65 near- and full-term neonates who underwent lung ultrasound (LUS) for suspected transient tachypnea of the newborn (TTN), 73% were diagnosed with TTN, 19% with pneumonia, 3.2% with respiratory distress syndrome (RDS), and 4.8% with meconium aspiration syndrome. The double-lung point showed a sensitivity of 69.6%, specificity of 100%, positive predictive value (PPV) of 100%, and negative predictive

value (NPV) of 39.1% for diagnosing TTN. Additionally, a positive correlation was observed between the severity of alveolar-interstitial syndrome (AIS) and the required oxygen support for TTN. LUS was found to be a reliable and non-invasive method for early TTN diagnosis and differentiation from other neonatal respiratory distress causes in Egyptian neonates.⁷⁷

In a prospective study conducted by Ibrahim M et al., (2018) to assess the lung US in early diagnosis of neonatal transient tachypnea and its differentiation. In a study of 65 neonates, 73.8% had transient tachypnea of the newborn (TTN), 18.5% had pneumonia, 4.6% had meconium aspiration syndrome (MAS), and 3.1% had respiratory distress syndrome (RDS). The double lung point demonstrated a sensitivity of 69.6%, specificity of 100%, positive predictive value (PPV) of 100%, and negative predictive value (NPV) of 39.1% for detecting TTN. The study also revealed a positive correlation between the severity of alveolar-interstitial syndrome (AIS) and the type of oxygen support required for TTN. Thus, lung ultrasound (LUS) is affirmed as a reliable and non-invasive method for early TTN diagnosis and differentiation from other neonatal respiratory distress causes in near and full-term Egyptian neonates.⁵⁸

In a study conducted by Jagla M et al., (2019) to assess the lung US in diagnosis of neonatal respiratory failure prior to the patient's transport. Lung Ultrasound (LUS) demonstrated a sensitivity of 91.3% and a specificity of 92.6% for diagnosing respiratory distress syndrome (RDS), outperforming chest X-ray (CXR), which had a sensitivity of 69.6% and a specificity of 81.5%. For diagnosing pneumothorax (PTX), LUS had a sensitivity of 83.3% and a specificity of 100%, compared to CXR's sensitivity of 16.7% and specificity of 97.7%. LUS showed substantial agreement with CXR ($\kappa = 0.57$) and

very good agreement with the final clinical diagnosis ($\kappa = 0.86$). LUS also identified the need for interventions like endotracheal tube repositioning or PTX decompression in 42% of cases before transport. Thus, LUS is a reliable tool for diagnosing respiratory issues in neonates and can improve care during transport.⁷⁸

In a study conducted by Li C et al., (2021) to assess the serial ultrasound for transient tachypnea in newborn. Out of 65 infants initially screened, 13 were excluded. Most infants in both the control and TTN (transient tachypnea of the newborn) groups showed their highest lung ultrasound (LUS) scores on the first day, which decreased over time. Compared to the control group, the TTN group had higher LUS scores on days 1 and 2 and experienced a more pronounced reduction in scores from day 1 to day 2. In the TTN group, LUS scores were moderately correlated with the severity of respiratory symptoms. In this study of late-preterm and term infants with TTN, serial quantitative LUS evaluations were performed. The LUS score effectively reflected the infants' respiratory condition and was useful for tracking the progression of TTN, whether it improved or worsened.⁷⁹

In a prospective study conducted by Louis D et al., (2021) to assess the prone versus supine position for lung US in neonates with respiratory distress. The study examined 64 neonates diagnosed mainly with transient tachypnea of the newborn (TTN) and respiratory distress syndrome (RDS). The Lung Ultrasound Scores (LUS) increased immediately after the neonates were placed in the prone position but returned to baseline after one hour. Specifically, LUS scores were higher shortly after the position change but similar to initial scores one hour later. This pattern held for TTN cases, while LUS scores remained

consistent across all three measurements in RDS cases. The study concluded that performing LUS in the prone position is feasible in neonates.⁸⁰

In a study conducted by Srinivasan S et al., (2022) assess the role of lung US in diagnosis and differentiating the transient tachypnea of newborn. Lung ultrasound (LUS) demonstrated 100% sensitivity and specificity in diagnosing transient tachypnea of the newborn (TTN) by identifying pulmonary edema with alveolo-interstitial syndrome, double lung point, or occasionally white-out lungs without consolidation. For respiratory distress syndrome (RDS), a combination of signs including consolidation with air or fluid bronchograms, white-out lungs, and absent spared areas also achieved 100% sensitivity and specificity. Notably, the double lung point was specific to TTN, while consolidation with bronchograms was exclusive to RDS. These findings indicate that LUS can accurately diagnose and differentiate TTN from RDS in preterm neonates, suggesting its potential as an initial screening tool in NICUs.⁸¹

In a study conducted by Loi B et al., (2023) to assess the respiratory and hemodynamic effect of 6h pronation in neonates recovering from respiratory distress syndrome. Between May 1, 2019, and May 31, 2021, 161 neonates were studied. Prone positioning significantly enhanced gas exchange and lung aeration ($p < 0.01$). These improvements reverted upon changing positions, except in neonates with neonatal acute respiratory distress syndrome (NARDS), where lung aeration benefits persisted. The positive effects were most pronounced in recovering respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) patients, followed by those with evolving bronchopulmonary dysplasia (BPD), and least in those with NARDS ($p < 0.01$). Lung ultrasound scores decreased from 16.9 in supine to 14.1 in prone ($p < 0.01$), indicating lung recruitment and correlated with improved oxygenation,

without affecting hemodynamic stability. Pronation for 6 hours enhances gas exchange and lung aeration in neonates with recovering RDS, evolving BPD, or NARDS, and does not significantly impact hemodynamic parameters.⁸²

In a prospective study conducted by Ismail R et al., (2023) to assess the lung ultrasound in diagnosis of neonatal respiratory disorders. The sensitivity and specificity of lung ultrasound (LUS) for diagnosing various neonatal respiratory disorders were: 94.7% and 100% for respiratory distress syndrome, 97.5% and 95% for pneumonia, 92.3% and 100% for meconium aspiration syndrome, 90.9% and 98.9% for pneumothorax, and 100% and 97.8% for pulmonary atelectasis. The overall diagnostic agreement between LUS and chest X-ray (CXR) was 98.5%, with a confidence interval of 0.88 to 0.92. These results suggest that LUS is a reliable and safer bedside diagnostic tool compared to CXR for neonatal respiratory disorders.⁸³

AIMS & OBJECTIVES

To study the comparison of scores of the lung ultrasound (LUS) in the prone positioning and to compare it with the supine positioning in neonates with respiratory distress.

To assess changes in Lung Ultrasound scores with the change in position of the neonate.

MATERIAL & METHOD

All newborns admitted to LEVEL IIIA Neonatal Intensive Care Unit (NICU), BLDE (Deemed to be University, Shri B. M. Patil Medical College Hospital and Research Centre, Vijayapura, Karnataka who meet the inclusion criteria.

Type of Study: It is a Prospective Observational Study

Duration of study: 12 months

Inclusion criteria

i) Neonates $>$ or equal to 29 weeks of gestational age with respiratory distress requiring respiratory support within the first 12 hours of life.

Exclusion criteria

- i) Gross congenital anomaly detected in the antenatal scan
- ii) sick infants whose position could not be changed.

SAMPLE SIZE:

Using G*Power ver. 3.1.9.4 software for sample size calculation, the proportion of Male babies, is 64%, this study requires a sample size of 102. So, to achieve a power of 81% for detecting a difference in Proportion (Exact - Proportion: Difference from constant (binomial test, one sample case) with a 5% level of significance.

Method

Neonates who are eligible were enrolled after obtaining informed consent from their parents. Three LUS was done on each neonate within the first 12 hours of life.

First LUS (fLUS): This was performed in whichever position, the neonate is nursed at the time of the enrolment, and care was taken to ensure that the infant remains in the new position for at least 2 hours before the fLUS was done.

Second LUS (sLUS): In this neonate will be turned to the other position (supine to prone or prone to supine), and the second LUS (sLUS) was performed immediately. Infants continued to be nursed in the same position as during the sLUS (as long as they tolerated that position),

Third LUS (tLUS): this was performed 1 to 2 hours after the sLUS.

Scoring Parameter:

The Scoring system divides each lung into six zones -

Upper anterior, lower anterior, upper axillary, lower axillary, upper posterior, lower posterior

The LUS score is assigned as follows:

0 - A-pattern (defined by the presence of the only A-lines);

1 - B-pattern (defined as the presence of ≥ 3 well-spaced B-lines);

2 - severe B-pattern (defined as the presence of crowded and coalescent B-lines with or without consolidations limited to the subpleural space); and

3 - extended consolidations.

STATISTICAL ANALYSIS

The data obtained is entered in a Microsoft Excel sheet, and statistical analyses are performed using a statistical package for the social sciences (SPSS) (Version 20). Results are presented as Mean, SD, counts and percentages, and diagrams. For normally distributed continuous variables between the two groups were compared using an independent sample test. For not normally distributed variables, the Mann-Whitney U test is used. For Categorical variables between the two groups, are compared using the Chi-square test/Fisher's exact test. If there are more than two groups used ANOVA, For not normally distributed, Kruskal-Walli H Test. If $p < 0.05$ was considered statistically significant. All statistics are performed two-tailed.

RESULTS

In present study total of 103 participants are included.

Table 1: Showing gender of newborn

		Count	Column N %
Gender	female	49	47.6%
	male	54	52.4%

Among the newborns, 52.4% were male and 47.6% were female.

Figure 10: Showing the mode of delivery

Table 2: Showing the mode of delivery

		Frequency	Percent
Mode of	Forceps	2	1.9

delivery	LSCS	62	60.2
	NVD	35	34.0
	Ventouse	4	3.9
	Total	103	100.0

The most common mode of delivery was LSCS in 60.2%, followed by NVD in 34% and 3.9% by ventouse.

Figure 11: Showing the mode of delivery

Table 3: Showing the mean gestational age and birth weight

	Mean	Standard Deviation
Gestational age	35.2	2.9
Birth weight	2.21	0.646

Among the patients mean gestational age was 35.2weeks. The mean birth weight of the newborn was found to be 2.2 ± 0.64

Figure 12: Showing the mean gestational age and birth weight

Table 4: Showing demographic details of the patients

		Count	Column N %
Classification	AGA	76	73.8%
	LGA	5	4.9%
	SGA	22	21.4%
Parity	Multi	51	49.5%
	Primi	52	50.5%
Socioeconomicstatus		5	4.9%
	lower	17	16.5%
	lower middle	31	30.1%
	Lower middle	1	1.0%
	upper	3	2.9%

	upper middle	46	44.7%
PIH	NO	78	75.7%
	Not known	3	2.9%
	YES	22	21.4%
GESTATIONAL DIABETES MELLITUS	NO	96	93.2%
	Not known	4	3.9%
	YES	3	2.9%
PROM/PPROM	NO	75	72.8%
	Not known	3	2.9%
	YES	25	24.3%
MATERNAL FEVER	NO	75	72.8%
	Not known	12	11.7%
	YES	16	15.5%
MATERNALUTI	No	83	80.6%
	Not known	15	14.6%
	YES	5	4.9%
MATERNAL CHORIOAMNIONITIS	NO	89	86.4%
	Not known	14	13.6%
ANTEPARTUM HEMORRHAGE	No	86	83.5%
	Not known	12	11.7%
	Yes	5	4.9%
H/O MATERNAL BLOOD TRANSFUSION	No	69	67.0%
	Not known	27	26.2%

	Yes	7	6.8%
MEDICAL DISORDERS	ANAMIA	25	24.3%
	ASTHMA	3	2.9%
	EPILEPSY	3	2.9%
	HYPOTHYROIDISM	2	1.9%
	NONE	70	68.0%
MATERNAL USG	ADEQUATE	55	53.4%
	NORMAL	18	17.5%
	NOT AVAILABLE	1	1.0%
	OLIGOHYDRAMNIOS	26	25.2%
	POLYHYDRAMNIOS	3	2.9%
DOPPLER UMBILICAL ARTERY	NORMAL	97	94.2%
	NOT DONE	4	3.9%
	REDUCED	2	1.9%
ANTENATAL STEROIDS	No	61	59.2%
	Yes	42	40.8%
CTG	NON REASSURING	5	4.9%
	NOT DONE	1	1.0%
	PATHOLOGICAL	1	1.0%
	REACTIVE	96	93.2%
MULTIPLE GESTATION	NONE	87	84.5%
	TWIN	16	15.5%

In patients PIH was present in 21.4%, GDM in 2.9%, maternal fever in 15.5%, UTI in 4.9%, antemartum hemorrhage 4.9%, antenatal steroids in 40.8%, multiple gestation in 15.5% of the patients.

Table 5: Showing distribution of APGAR score among patients

		Count	Column N %
APGAR1MIN	6.0	3	2.9%
	7.0	49	47.6%
	8.0	51	49.5%
APGAR5MIN	7.0	4	3.9%
	8.0	27	26.2%
	9.0	72	69.9%

APGAR score was found to be 49.5% with 8 in 1st min and 69.9% with 9 score at 5th min.

Figure 13: Showing distribution of APGAR score among patients

Table 6: Showing the gestational status, and respiratory support among patients

		Count	Column N %
Meconium stained	NO	89	86.4%
	YES	14	13.6%
Gestational age	early preterm (<30w)	4	3.9%
	late preterm (34w-37w)	41	39.8%
	mid preterm (30-34w)	28	27.2%
	TERM	30	29.1%
Sas score admission	0-2	66	64.1%
	3-4	37	35.9%
Primary respiratory support	CPAP	37	35.9%
	HFNC	23	22.3%
	HOOD	38	36.9%

	Nasal O2	1	1.0%
	NASAL O2	4	3.9%

Figure 14: Showing the gestational age at delivery

Figure 15: Showing type of primary respiratory support provided

Table 7: Showing oxygen status at admission

	Mean	Standard Deviation
FIO2 on admission	35.2	5.6
SPO2 on admission	95.6	1.4

The mean level of the FIO2 and SpO2 on admission is presented in the table.

*Figure 16: Showing oxygen status at admission**Table 8: Distribution of sepsis and respiratory concern among patients*

		Count	Column N %
Sepsis	Early onset	93	90.3%
	Late onset	10	9.7%
Sepsis	Clinical	41	39.8%
	Probable	53	51.5%

	Proven	9	8.7%
Respiratory concern	Apnea	1	1.0%
	Cong pneumonia	1	1.0%
	HIE	1	1.0%
	MAS	10	9.7%
	RDS	60	58.3%
	RDS, APNEA	3	2.9%
	RDS, APNEA, HIE	1	1.0%
	RDS, HIE	3	2.9%
	RDS, MAS	1	1.0%
	TTNB	21	20.4%
	TTNB, MAS	1	1.0%
CNS CONCERN	Congenital malformations	1	1.0%
	Intra ventriculatr hemorrhage	5	4.9%
	Normal	93	90.3%
	Periventricular hemorrhage	4	3.9%

Sepsis was early onset in 90.3% and late onset in 9.7% of the patients.

Figure 17: Showing the respiratory concern among patients

Table 9: Showing distribution of antibiotics used and support given to patients

	Count	Column N %
Antibiotics	Amkacin	6 5.8%
	Amkacin, Mero	2 1.9%
	Amkacin, Taxim	1 1.0%
	Mero	3 2.9%
	Mero, Vanco	2 1.9%
	No Antibiotics	20 19.4%
	Piptaz	50 48.5%
	Piptaz, Amkacin	10 9.7%
	Piptaz, Mero, Vanco	1 1.0%
	Taxim	7 6.8%
	Vanco	1 1.0%

Delayed perinatal adaptation	No	78	75.7%
	YES	25	24.3%
HIE	NO	90	87.4%
	YES	12	11.7%
SUPPORTIN AT 2HOURS	CPAP	38	36.9%
	HFNC	24	23.3%
	HOOD	37	35.9%
	Nasal prongs	1	1.0%
	NASAL PRONGS	3	2.9%
PPHN	No	92	89.3%
	YES	11	10.7%
SUPPORT	CPAP	37	35.9%
	HFNC	24	23.3%
	HOOD	38	36.9%
	NASAL PRONGS	4	3.9%

Delayed perinatal adaptation is present in 34.3%, HIE was present in 11.7%, PPHN present in 10.7% and support of CPAP in 35.9%, Hood in 36.9% of cases.

Table 10: Showing mean hematological parameters

	Mean	Standard Deviation
Hemoglobin	17.2	2.4

Total count	14706.7	4868.0
Platelet count	228889.1	80729.8
Time interval between admission to abg	17.4	6.7
Spo2 during abg	95.5	1.3

Table showing the mean level of hematological parameters.

Figure 18: Showing mean hematological parameters

Table 11: Showing mean oxygen saturation at different scan

	Mean	Standard Deviation
Time interval between admission to ABG	17.4	6.7
SPO2 during abg	95.5	1.3
SPO2 on 1 st scan	95.8	1.6
SPO2 on 2 nd scan	96.1	2.0

SPO2 on 3 rd scan	95.4	9.5
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Figure 19: Showing mean oxygen saturation at different scan

Table 12: Showing distribution of results of ABG among patients

		Count	Column N %
ABG PH	<7	1	1.0%
	>7.3	56	54.4%
	7-7.19	11	10.7%
	7.2-7.29	35	34.0%
ABG PaO2	>60	96	93.2%
	50-60	7	6.8%
ABG PaCO2	<50	72	69.9%
	50-60	31	30.1%

ABG HCO ₃	<10	14	13.6%
	11-15	73	70.9%
	16-20	13	12.6%
	20-24	2	1.9%
LACTATE	<2	8	7.8%
	>2	95	92.2%

Table showing the ABG analysis report of the patients.

Table 13: Showing oxygen saturation among patients

	Mean	Standard Deviation
PO ₂ FIO ₂	3.68	.99
SPO ₂ during ABG	95.7	1.4
FIO ₂	35.3	5.0
Base excess 24min usbicarb	11.0	2.7

Figure 20: Showing oxygen saturation among patients

Table 14: Showing the interval of LUS, chest X-ray scoring

		Count	Column N %
LUS interval in minutes		46	44.7%
	>120	2	1.9%
	30	9	8.7%
	31-60	38	36.9%
	61-90	8	7.8%
CXR scoring	.0	55	53.4%
	1.0	25	24.3%
	2.0	17	16.5%
	3.0	5	4.9%
	4.0	1	1.0%

The CXR scoring was found to be 0 in majority, followed by 1 score in 24.3% of cases.

SUPINE POSITION

Table 15: Oxygen saturation at supine position

	Mean	Standard Deviation
SPO2 during CX RAY	95.8	1.4
SPO2 during LUS	96.0	1.5
FIO2	35.3	5.2
SPO2 at 2 ND LUS	96.0	1.5

Showing the mean level of the parameters in supine position

Figure 21: Oxygen saturation at supine position

Table 16: Showing the ABG result distribution in supine position

		Count	Column N %
SUPPORT	CPAP	38	36.9%
	HFNC	23	22.3%
	HOOD	37	35.9%
	Nasal prongs	1	1.0%
	NASAL PRONGS	3	2.9%
	ROOM AIR	1	1.0%
ABG PH	>7.3	47	45.6%
	7-7.19	1	1.0%
	7.2-7.29	21	20.4%
ABG PaO2	>60	63	61.2%
	50-60	6	5.8%
ABG PaCO2	<50	55	53.4%
	50-60	13	12.6%
ABG HCO3	11-15	40	38.8%
	16-20	26	25.2%
	20-24	2	1.9%
ABG LACTATE	<2	26	25.2%
	>2	42	40.8%

Table 17: Showing the oxygen parameter and base excess in supine position

	Mean	Standard Deviation
PaO2FIO2	5.3	11.3
BASEEXCESS	8.8	2.6

Showing the distribution of parameters in supine position

PRONE POSITION

Table 18: Showing the oxygen saturation in prone position

	Mean	Standard Deviation
SPO2 during USG	96.2	1.5
FIO2	35.3	5.2
SPO2 at 3rd LUS	96.1	1.1
PaO2FIO2	4.55	1.30
Base excess	8.0	2.9

Table showing the mean level in prone position.

Figure 22: Showing the oxygen saturation in prone position

Table 19: Showing the respiratory support and ABG result

		Count	Column N %
SUPPORT	CPAP	38	36.9%
	HFNC	22	21.4%
	HOOD	38	36.9%
	NASAL PRONGS	4	3.9%
	ROOM AIR	1	1.0%
ABGPH	>7.3	31	30.1%
	7-7.19	1	1.0%
	7.2-7.29	5	4.9%
ABGPaO2	>60	35	34.0%
	50-60	1	1.0%
ABGPaCO2	<50	36	35.0%

	50-60	1	1.0%
ABGHCO3	<10	1	1.0%
	11-15	12	11.7%
	16-20	19	18.4%
	20-24	4	3.9%
ABGLACTATE	<2	26	25.2%
	>2	10	9.7%

Table showing the distribution of the parameters in prone position.

Table 20: Comparison of the parameters between supine and prone position

Paired Samples Statistics		Mean	Std. Deviation	p-value
Pair 1	S_SPO2DURINGLUS	96.000	1.5642	0.304
	P_SPO2DURINGUSG	96.179	1.4802	
Pair 2	FIO2	35.206	5.1863	0.566
	FIO2	35.304	5.1814	
Pair 3	S_SPO2AT2NDLUS	95.948	1.4680	0.257
	P_SPO2AT3RDLUS	96.125	1.1355	
Pair 4	S_PaO2FIO2	4.449	1.1984	0.21
	PaO2FIO2	4.5986	1.32190	
Pair 5	S_BASEEXCESS	9.514	2.5938	0.01*
	BASEEXCESS	7.966	2.9595	

There is no significant difference in the mean level of the SpO₂, FiO₂, SpO₂, PaO₂/FiO₂ between the two methods. However the mean level of base excess was significantly higher in supine position.

Figure 23: Comparison of the parameters between supine and prone position

Table 21: Comparison of the pH with supine and prone position

		P_ABGPH_B					
		>7.3		7-7.19		7.2-7.29	
		Count	N %	Count	N %	Count	N %
S_ABGPH_A	>7.3	22	71.0%	0	0.0%	1	20.0%
	7-7.19	0	0.0%	1	100.0%	0	0.0%

	7.2-7.29	8	25.8%	0	0.0%	3	60.0%
Chi-square (p-value)		127.87 (0.01)*					

There is significant correlation of the pH in supine and prone position.

Figure 24: Comparison of the pH with supine and prone position

Table 22: Comparison of oxygen saturation between the position

		P_ABGPaO2_B					
				>60		50-60	
		Count	N %	Count	N %	Count	N %
S_ABGPaO2_A		33	49.3%	1	2.9%	0	0.0%
	>60	28	41.8%	34	97.1%	1	100.0%
	50-60	6	9.0%	0	0.0%	0	0.0%
Chi-square (p-value)		30.315 (0.01)*					

There is significant correlation of PaO₂, in prone and supine position.

Figure 25: Comparison of oxygen saturation between the position

Table 23: Comparison of the carbon dioxide with position of patients

		P_ABGPaCO ₂ _B					
				<50		50-60	
		Count	N %	Count	N %	Count	N %
S_ABGPaCO ₂ _A		32	48.5%	3	8.3%	0	0.0%
	<50	24	36.4%	31	86.1%	0	0.0%
	50-60	10	15.2%	2	5.6%	1	100.0%
Chi-square (p-value)		30.53 (0.01)*					

There is significant correlation of PaCO₂ between the supine and prone position.

Figure 26: Comparison of the carbon dioxide with position of patients

Table 24: Comparison of the bicarbonate level with position of the patient

		P_ABGHCO3_B									
				<10		11-15		16-20		20-24	
		Co	N	Co	N %	Co	N	Co	N	Co	N
		unt	%	unt	%	unt	%	unt	%	unt	%
S_ABGH CO3_A		33	49.	0	0.0	1	8.3	1	5.3	0	0.0
			3%		%		%		%		%
	1	14	20.	1	100.	11	91.	12	63.	2	50.
	1		9%		0%		7%		2%		0%
	-										
	1	19	28.	0	0.0	0	0.0	6	31.	1	25.

	6		4%		%		%		6%		0%
	-										
	2										
	0										
	2	1	1.5	0	0.0	0	0.0	0	0.0	1	25.
	0		%		%		%		%		0%
	-										
	2										
	4										
Chi-square (p-value)	46.88 (0.01)*										

There is significant correlation of bicarbonate level between the supine and prone position.

Figure 27: Comparison of the bicarbonate level with position of the patient

Table 25: Comparison of the lactate level with position of patients

		P_ABGLACTATE_A					
				<2		>2	
		Count	N %	Count	N %	Count	N %
S_ABGLACTATE		33	49.3%	2	7.7%	0	0.0%
	<2	12	17.9%	14	53.8%	0	0.0%
	>2	22	32.8%	10	38.5%	10	100.0%
Chi-square (p-value)		35.33 (0.01)*					

There is significant correlation of the ABG lactate between levels more than 2.(p<0.05)

Figure 28: Comparison of the lactate level with position of patients

Table 26: Comparison of overall mean difference between the scores (n=103).

Overall	Mean	SD	p-value
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Pair 1	Score 1st video	2.990	2.43	0.01*
	Score 2nd video	2.350	2.08	
Pair 2	Score 1st video	2.990	2.43	0.01*
	Score 3rd video	1.883	1.94	
Pair 3	Score 2nd video	2.350	2.08	0.01*
	Score 3rd video	1.883	1.94	

Overall, there is significant higher mean score 1st video compared to the patients in score in 3rd and 2nd video.

Figure 29: Comparison of overall mean difference between the scores

Table 27: Comparison of the video scores in newborns with TTNB based on lung ultrasound (n=36)

		Patients with TTNB		Paired t-test
		Mean	SD	p-value
Pair 1	Score 1st video	2.6	2.8	0.01*
	Score 2nd video	2.2	2.0	
Pair 2	Score 1st video	2.6	2.8	0.01*
	Score 3rd video	1.3	1.4	
Pair 3	Score 2nd video	2.2	2.0	0.01*
	Score 3rd video	1.3	1.4	

In the study the mean score of 1st video was significantly higher compared to the score on 3rd video and 2nd video in patients with TTNB. ($p < 0.05$)

Figure 30: Comparison of the video scores in patients with TTNB

Table 28: Comparison of the video scores in newborns with Non TTNB based on lung ultrasound (n=48)

		Non TTNB		Paired t-test
		Mean	SD	p-value
Pair 1	Score 1st video	3.1	2.4	0.56
	Score 2nd video	2.9	1.6	
Pair 2	Score 1st video	3.1	2.4	0.65
	Score 3rd video	2.5	1.9	
Pair 3	Score 2nd video	2.9	1.6	0.24
	Score 3rd video	2.5	1.9	

In the study there is higher mean score of 1st video with 3rd and 2nd video mean, however there is no significant difference.

Figure 31: Comparison of the video scores in patients with Non TTNB

Table 29: Comparison of the X-ray diagnosis with USG diagnosis

X-ray Diagnosis	USG Diagnosis			Chi Square value
	Non TTNB (n=48)	Normal (n=19)	TTNB (n=36)	
Non TTNB (n=44)	35 (72.9%)	0	9 (25%)	15.38 (0.01) *
Normal (n=29)	2 (4.16%)	19 (100%)	8 (22.2%)	
TTNB (n=30)	11 (22.9%)	0	19 (52.7%)	

There is significant correlation of the x-ray with the USG diagnosis of TTNB.

Figure 32: Comparison of the X-ray diagnosis with USG diagnosis

DISCUSSION

Lung ultrasound (LUS) has emerged as a critical diagnostic tool in managing neonates with respiratory distress, offering real-time, non-invasive imaging that aids in assessing lung pathology. Traditional imaging techniques, like chest radiography, present limitations, including radiation exposure and reduced sensitivity for certain pulmonary conditions. In contrast, LUS provides dynamic visualization of lung parenchyma and pleural surfaces without ionizing radiation, making it highly suitable for fragile neonatal patients.

The choice of patient positioning during LUS—prone versus supine—has become a topic of increasing interest and debate. Each position influences the distribution of pulmonary fluids, lung aeration, and the ease of access to various lung zones, potentially affecting the accuracy and diagnostic value of LUS findings. The supine position is more commonly used due to ease of access and monitoring; however, the prone position, which is often employed in neonates with certain respiratory conditions, may offer distinct advantages by enhancing lung mechanics and improving ventilation-perfusion matching.

Evaluating the efficacy of prone versus supine positioning for LUS in neonates with respiratory distress is crucial. It provides insights into optimizing diagnostic accuracy and enhancing clinical outcomes by tailoring imaging techniques to the physiological needs of neonatal patients. This discussion aims to explore the advantages, limitations, and clinical implications of each position in the context of LUS for neonates, contributing to evidence-based practices in neonatal respiratory care.

In present study total of 103 participants are included. Among the newborns mean gestational age was 35.2weeks, 52.4% were male and 47.6% were female. The most common mode of delivery was LSCS in 60.2%, followed by NVD in 34% and 3.9% by ventouse.

The mean birth weight of the newborn was found to be 2.2 ± 0.64 . In patients PIH was present in 21.4%, GDM in 2.9%, maternal fever in 15.5%, UTI in 4.9%, antepartum haemorrhage 4.9%, antenatal steroids in 40.8%, multiple gestation in 15.5% of the patients. APGAR score was found to be 49.5% with 8 in 1st min and 69.9% with 9 score at 5th min.

In study by Ibrahim M et al., documented full-term neonates who underwent lung ultrasound (LUS) for suspected transient tachypnea of the newborn (TTN), 73% were diagnosed with TTN, 19% with pneumonia, 3.2% with respiratory distress syndrome (RDS), and 4.8% with meconium aspiration syndrome.⁷⁷

There is no significant difference in the mean level of the SpO₂, FiO₂, PaO₂/FIO₂ between the two positions. However, the mean level of base excess was significantly higher in supine position. There is significant correlation of the pH, PaO₂, PaCO₂ between the supine and prone position. Also, significant correlation of bicarbonate, lactate level between the supine and prone position.

Gargani et al. showed that sonographic abnormalities in the lung precede PaO₂/Fio₂ changes in an animal model. Therefore, LUS can be easily used for the early detection of patients with NRDS before clinical deterioration and improve the clinical progression and prognosis.²⁴ Li C et al., found that the TTN group, LUS scores were moderately correlated with the severity of respiratory symptoms. In this study of late-preterm and term infants with TTN, serial quantitative LUS evaluations were performed. The LUS score effectively

reflected the infants' respiratory condition and was useful for tracking the progression of TTN, whether it improved or worsened.⁷⁹

In line study by Loi B et al., documented with Prone positioning significantly enhanced gas exchange and lung aeration ($p < 0.01$). These improvements reverted upon changing positions, except in neonates with neonatal acute respiratory distress syndrome (NARDS), where lung aeration benefits persisted. The positive effects were most pronounced in recovering respiratory distress syndrome (RDS) patients, followed by those with evolving bronchopulmonary dysplasia (BPD), and least in those with NARDS ($p < 0.01$). Lung ultrasound scores decreased from 16.9 in supine to 14.1 in prone ($p < 0.01$), indicating lung recruitment and correlated with improved oxygenation, without affecting hemodynamic stability. Pronation for 6 hours enhances gas exchange and lung aeration in neonates with recovering RDS, evolving BPD, or NARDS, and does not significantly impact hemodynamic parameters.⁸²

Overall, there is significant higher mean score 1st video compared to the patients in score in 3rd and 2nd video. In the study the mean score of 1st video was significantly higher compared to the score on 3rd video and 2nd video in patients with TTNB. ($p < 0.05$) There is significant correlation of the X-ray and USG diagnosis with clinical diagnosis among the patients.

Similar to present study Copetti et al., diagnosed RDS with three USG findings and profile had a sensitivity and specificity of 100% in their series of 55 premature infants. The high diagnostic accuracy may allow a better individualized surfactant administration, saving costs and minimizing the duration of ineffective breathing.⁷⁵

Another study by Ibrahim M et al., documented double-lung point showed a sensitivity of 69.6%, specificity of 100%, positive predictive value (PPV) of 100%, and negative predictive value (NPV) of 39.1% for diagnosing TTN. Additionally, a positive correlation was observed between the severity of alveolar-interstitial syndrome (AIS) and the required oxygen support for TTN. LUS was found to be a reliable and non-invasive method for early TTN diagnosis and differentiation from other neonatal respiratory distress causes in Egyptian neonates.⁷⁷

In concordance to present study Jagla M et al., Lung Ultrasound (LUS) demonstrated a sensitivity of 91.3% and a specificity of 92.6% for diagnosing respiratory distress syndrome (RDS), outperforming chest X-ray (CXR), which had a sensitivity of 69.6% and a specificity of 81.5%. For diagnosing pneumothorax (PTX), LUS had a sensitivity of 83.3% and a specificity of 100%, compared to CXR's sensitivity of 16.7% and specificity of 97.7%. LUS showed substantial agreement with CXR ($\kappa = 0.57$) and very good agreement with the final clinical diagnosis ($\kappa = 0.86$). LUS also identified the need for interventions like endotracheal tube repositioning or PTX decompression in 42% of cases before transport. Thus, LUS is a reliable tool for diagnosing respiratory issues in neonates and can improve care during transport.⁷⁸

Another study by Ismail R et al., documented with sensitivity and specificity of lung ultrasound (LUS) for diagnosing various neonatal respiratory disorders were: 94.7% and 100% for respiratory distress syndrome, 97.5% and 95% for pneumonia, 92.3% and 100% for meconium aspiration syndrome, 90.9% and 98.9% for pneumothorax, and 100% and 97.8% for pulmonary atelectasis. The overall diagnostic agreement between LUS and chest X-ray (CXR) was 98.5%, with a confidence interval of 0.88 to 0.92. These results

suggest that LUS is a reliable and safer bedside diagnostic tool compared to CXR for neonatal respiratory disorders.⁸³

Our study on lung ultrasound (LUS) positioning in 103 neonates with respiratory distress found no significant differences in key respiratory parameters (SpO₂, FiO₂, PaO₂/FiO₂) between prone and supine positions. The cohort, with a mean gestational age of 35.2 weeks and a nearly equal gender distribution, predominantly underwent LSCS (60.2%) for delivery. Maternal factors like PIH (21.4%) and antenatal steroids (40.8%) influenced neonatal profiles. While the supine position had a higher mean base excess, significant correlations in pH, PaO₂, PaCO₂, bicarbonate, and ABG lactate levels between positions indicate consistent physiological responses. Significant alignment between clinical diagnoses and imaging findings from X-ray and ultrasound was also noted, particularly for TTNB. Both positions provide comparable diagnostic value, but differences in blood gas correlations suggest the need for individualized position assessment in neonatal LUS.

SUMMARY

- In present study total of 103 newborns were included.
- Among the newborns mean gestational age was 35.2weeks.
- Among the newborns, 52.4% were male and 47.6% were female.
- The most common mode of delivery was LSCS in 60.2%, followed by NVD in 34% and 3.9% by ventouse.
- The mean birth weight of the newborn was found to be 2.2 ± 0.64
- In patients PIH was present in 21.4%, GDM in 2.9%, maternal fever in 15.5%, UTI in 4.9%, antepartum haemorrhage 4.9%, antenatal steroids in 40.8%, multiple gestation in 15.5% of the patients.
- APGAR score was found to be 49.5% with 8 in 1st min and 69.9% with 9 score at 5th min.
- The mean level of the FIO₂ and SpO₂ on admission is presented in the table.
- Sepsis was early onset in 90.3% and late onset in 9.7% of the patients.
- There is no significant difference in the mean level of the SpO₂, FiO₂, PaO₂/FIO₂ between the two methods. However, the mean level of base excess was significantly higher in supine position.
- There is significant correlation of the pH in supine and prone position.
- There is significant correlation of PaO₂, in prone and supine position
- There is significant correlation of PaCO₂ between the supine and prone position
- There is significant correlation of bicarbonate level between the supine and prone position.

- There is significant correlation of the ABG lactate between levels more than 2. (p<0.05)
- Overall, there is significant higher mean score 1st video compared to the patients in score in 3rd and 2nd video.
- In the study the mean score of 1st video was significantly higher compared to the score on 3rd video and 2nd video in patients with TTNB. (p<0.05)
- In the study there is higher mean score of 1st video with 3rd and 2nd video mean, however there is no significant difference.
- There is significant correlation of the X-ray and USG diagnosis with clinical diagnosis among the patients.
- There is significant correlation of the x-ray with the USG diagnosis of TTNB.

CONCLUSION

In the assessment of lung ultrasound (LUS) positioning for neonates with respiratory distress, our study involving 103 newborns has provided valuable insights into the relative effectiveness of prone versus supine positioning. With a mean gestational age of 35.2 weeks and a gender distribution of 52.4% males and 47.6% females, this cohort predominantly underwent LSCS (60.2%) for delivery. Maternal factors, such as PIH (21.4%), GDM (2.9%), and the use of antenatal steroids (40.8%), contributed to the neonatal profiles.

Despite the variations in delivery modes and maternal conditions, our findings indicate no significant differences in key respiratory parameters (FiO_2 , PaO_2/FiO_2) between the prone and supine positions. However, the supine position was associated with a significantly higher mean base excess. Additionally, there were significant correlations in pH, PaO_2 , $PaCO_2$, bicarbonate, and ABG lactate levels between both positions, suggesting consistency in the physiological responses to the positioning during LUS.

Notably, our data showed a significant correlation between clinical diagnoses and imaging findings from X-ray and ultrasound, particularly in cases of transient tachypnea of the newborn (TTNB). The mean scores for initial video assessments were significantly higher compared to subsequent evaluations, emphasizing the importance of initial diagnostic imaging and subsequent imaging after change in the positioning of newborn in cases of TTNB.

Overall, changing the positioning from prone to supine position or supine to prone for LUS and scoring in neonates with respiratory distress provide comparable diagnostic

utility. However, the observed differences in correlations across various blood gas parameters underscore the need for individualized assessment when selecting the optimal position.

To conclude, this study's findings show that lung ultrasonography may reliably detect and distinguish between TTN and non TTN diseases, though Lung ultrasound in neonates offers several advantages but also comes with specific challenges limitations like operator dependency, positioning issues, equipment limitations, training requirements, and the chest radiography cannot match the additional benefits of lung ultrasonography. Thus, in neonatal intensive care units, lung ultrasonography can be utilized as a screening technique to detect lung disease at an early stage. Future research should continue to refine our understanding of how positioning impacts LUS accuracy and clinical outcomes in this vulnerable population, ensuring that neonatal care is both precise and effective.

CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS

Lung ultrasound in neonates offers several advantages but also comes with specific challenges and limitations:

Challenges:

1. **Operator Dependency:** Skill and experience of the operator significantly affect the quality and interpretation of ultrasound images. Training is crucial to achieve consistency and accuracy.

2. **Interpretation Complexity:** Differentiating various lung pathologies (e.g., atelectasis, pneumothorax) from normal lung patterns can be challenging, especially in preterm infants with immature lungs.
3. **Positioning Issues:** Proper positioning of the neonate for optimal imaging may be difficult, especially in critically ill or ventilated infants.
4. **Time-Consuming:** Performing a thorough lung ultrasound may take more time compared to other imaging modalities, which can be a limitation in acute clinical settings.

Limitations:

1. **Air Interference:** Air in the lungs creates artifacts that may obscure underlying pathology, such as pneumothorax or consolidations, making interpretation challenging.
2. **Limited Diagnostic Scope:** While useful for detecting pneumothorax, consolidations, and other lung pathologies, ultrasound may not provide comprehensive information about underlying causes (e.g., infection, pulmonary haemorrhage).
3. **Inability for Certain Diagnoses:** Some conditions, such as cystic lung diseases or pulmonary malformations, may not be adequately visualized or diagnosed with ultrasound alone.

4. **Training Requirements:** Adequate training and ongoing proficiency maintenance are necessary for accurate and reliable interpretation, which may not always be universally available.

5. **Comparative Data with Other Modalities:** In some cases, ultrasound findings may need to be correlated with findings from chest X-ray or CT scan for a more comprehensive assessment.

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ANNEXURE I

BLDE

(DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY)
Declared as Deemed to be University u/s 3 of UGC Act, 1956
Accredited with 'A' Grade by NAAC (Cycle-2)

The Constituent College

SHRI B. M. PATIL MEDICAL COLLEGE, HOSPITAL & RESEARCH CENTRE, VIJAYAPURA
BLDE (DU)/IEC/ 656/2022-23 30/8/2022

INSTITUTIONAL ETHICAL CLEARANCE CERTIFICATE

The Ethical Committee of this University met on Friday, 26th August, 2022 at 3.30 p.m. in the Department of Pharmacology scrutinizes the Synopsis of Post Graduate Student of BLDE (DU)'s Shri B.M.Patil Medical College Hospital & Research Centre from ethical clearance point of view. After scrutiny, the following original/ corrected and revised version synopsis of the thesis/ research projects has been accorded ethical clearance.

TITLE: "PRONE -V/S SUPINE POSITION FOR LUNG ULTRASOUND IN NEONATES WITH RESPIRATORY DISTRESS".

NAME OF THE STUDENT/PRINCIPAL INVESTIGATOR: DR. Y ROHITH

NAME OF THE GUIDE: Dr M.M Patil, Professor, Dept. of Pediatrics.

Dr. Santoshkumar Jeevangi
Chairperson
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA
Chairman,
Institutional Ethical Committee,
BLDE (Deemed to be University)
Vijayapura

Dr. Akram A. Naikwadi
Member Secretary
IEC, BLDE (DU),
VIJAYAPURA
MEMBER SECRETARY
Institutional Ethics Committee
BLDE (Deemed to be University),
Vijayapura-586103, Karnataka

Following documents were placed before Ethical Committee for Scrutinization.

- Copy of Synopsis/Research Projects
- Copy of inform consent form
- Any other relevant document

Smt. Bangaramma Sajjan Campus, B. M. Patil Road (Sholapur Road), Vijayapura - 586103, Karnataka, India.
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ANNEXURE II

RESEARCH INFORMED CONSENT FORM

BLDEDU (DEEMED TO BE UNIVERSITY) Shri B.M. PATIL Medical College,
Hospital & Research Centre, Vijayapura, Karnataka -586103.

TITLE OF THE PROJECT:

**“PRONE VERSUS SUPINE POSITION FOR LUNG ULTRASOUND
IN THE NEONATES WITH RESPIRATORY DISTRESS”**

GUIDE

DR.M M PATIL MD

PROFESSOR

DEPARTMENT OF PEDIATRICS

CO GUIDE

DR. RAVI KUMAR DNB

PROFESSOR

DEPARTMENT OF RADIOLOGY

PG STUDENT

DR. Y. ROHITH

PURPOSE OF RESEARCH

TO COMPARE PRONE VERSUS SUPINE POSITION FOR LUNG ULTRASOUND IN
NEONATES WITH RESPIRATORY DISTRESS

PROCEDURE:

I understand that after having obtained a detailed clinical history, thorough clinical examination and relevant investigations, a final workup of the procedure and its outcome is planned.

RISK AND DISCOMFORTS:

I understand that I may experience some pain and discomfort during the examination or during my treatment. This is mainly the result of my condition and the procedures of this study are not expected to exaggerate these feelings, which are associated with the usual course of treatment.

BENEFITS:

I understand that my participation in the study will have no direct benefit to me other than the potential benefit of the treatment.

CONFIDENTIALITY:

I understand that the medical information produced by this study will become a part of hospital records and will be subject to confidentiality. Information of sensitive personal nature will not be part of the medical record but will be stored in the investigations research file. If the data are used for publication in the medical literature or for teaching purposes, no name will be used, and other identifiers such as photographs will be used only with special written permission. I understand that I may see the photograph before giving the permission

REQUEST FOR MORE INFORMATION:

I understand that I may ask more questions about the study at any time; Dr. Y. Rohith at the department of pediatrics is available to answer my questions or concerns. I understand that I will be informed of any significant new findings discovered during the course of the study, which might influence my continued participation. A copy of this consent form will be given to me to keep for careful reading.

REFUSAL FOR WITHDRAWAL OF PARTICIPATION:

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I may refuse to participate or may withdraw consent and discontinue participation in the study at any time without prejudice. I also understand that Dr. Y Rohith may terminate my participation in the study after he/she has explained the reasons for doing so.

INJURY STATEMENT:

I understand that in the unlikely event of injury to my child resulting directly from child's participation in this study, if such injury were reported promptly, the appropriate treatment would be available to the child. But no further compensation would be provided by the hospital. I understand that by my agreement to participate in this study and not waiving any of my legal rights.

I have explained to _____ the purpose of the research, the procedures required and the possible risks to the best of my ability

DR. Y. ROHITH
(Investigator)

Date

PARENTS / GUARDIAN CONSENT STATEMENT:

We confirm that Dr. Y. Rohith is doing a study on "prone versus supine position for lung ultrasound in the neonates with respiratory distress" in Shri B. M. Patil Medical College Hospital Vijayapura, Karnataka. Dr. Y. Rohith has explained to us the purpose of research and the study procedure. We are willing to allow our child to get treated in Shri B.M. Patil Medical College Hospital, Vijayapura. We have been explained about the study, benefits and possible discomforts in detail in our native language and we understand the same. We are aware that the child will get the best treatment and no compensation like financial benefits will be given if our child's condition deteriorates and any untoward event happens, and we will not sue anyone regarding this. Therefore, we agree to give our full consent for child's participation as a subject in this research project.

(Parents / Guardian)

Date

(Witness to signature)

Date

ANNEXURE III

PROFORMA

1. Baby of:
2. IP No:
3. Date of Birth:
4. Gestational Age:
5. Time of birth:
6. Classification: AGA / SGA/ LGA
7. Sex:
8. Birth weight:
9. MODE OF DELIVERY: Normal vaginal/caesarean/forceps/vacuum
10. LSCS Indication -
11. Parity – PRIMIGRAVIDA / MULTIGRAVIDA
12. Socioeconomic status - LOWER / LOWER MIDDLE / UPPER MIDDLE / UPPER MIDDLE/UPPER
13. Residential area -
14. NICU admission in hours:
15. Primary Respiratory Support: Nasal Prongs/Hood O2/CPAP/HFNC/SIMV
Number of days on respiratory support:
16. Respiratory instability: apnoea, tachypnoea, increased o2 requirement/
Requirement for ventilation support: YES NO

No of days on ventilator

19. Lab Parameter:

- a) White blood cells count
- b) Immature to total neutrophil count
- c) Platelet count
- d) Platelet count /Lymphocyte Ratio
- e) Platelet distribution width
- f) Neutrophil –Lymphocyte Count Ratio (NLCR)
- g) CRP
- h) Absolute Neutrophil Count
- i) Hyperglycaemia
- j) Hypoglycaemia (glucose <45mg/dl)
- k) Arterial Blood gas analysis
 - ph
 - Pco₂
 - Po₂
 - Hco₃
 - Metabolic acidosis with base excess (BE)
 - Serum lactate >2mMol/l
- l) Blood Culture

27. Late onset sepsis YES NO

28. Late onset sepsis a) Clinical b) Probable c) Proven

29. Antibiotics received amongst below

a) Piptaz b) Amikacin c) Meropenem d) Vancomycin

d) Linezolid e) Colistin f) Amphotericin B

30. Culture positive in first 72 hours YES NO

If culture positive Organism

37. Final outcome a) Discharged b) Referred c) DAMA d)Death

38. Length of stay if discharged /DAMA

39. LUNG ULTRASOUND SCORING

LUS	RIGHT			LEFT		
	1	2	3	1	2	3
UPPER ANTERIOR						
LOWER ANTERIOR						
UPPER AXILLARY						
LOWER AXILLARY						
UPPER POSTERIOR						
LOWER POSTERIOR						

BIODATA OF THE GUIDE

NAME : Dr. M M PATIL

EDUCATION : M B B S – KIMS HUBLI
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KMC REGISTRATION NUMBER : 52830

WORK EXPERIENCE : UG TEACHER EXPERIENCE – 14 YEARS
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